

IMPACT OF STUDENTS' MOTIVATION AND DISCIPLINE ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN HAMISI SUB-COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract:

High Motivation for academic achievement among students and good to excellent academic discipline are undoubtedly key elements of high academic achievement among students at any level of schooling and cannot be gainsaid. A highly motivated and disciplined student is a self-starter and embraces positive initiative in academics. Such a student is bound to perform better in any standardized examination and has an increased chance for future study and better careers. This study attempted to analyze motivation and discipline as student-related factors affecting academic achievement in secondary schools in Hamisi sub-county, Vihiga-Kenya with focus on students who score high grades in primary school's KCPE vis-à-vis what they achieve at secondary school's KCSE. The study was guided by the following objectives: 1. To determine the effect of students' motivation to students' academic achievement in secondary schools and 2. To ascertain student discipline levels and its effect to student' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county, Kenya. The study employed descriptive survey research design. The target population was 4,298 consisting of 41 Principals, 428 teachers, 3826 students, 1 DEO and 2 AEOs. The sample size was 525 respondents consisting of 12 principals, 128 teachers, 383 students, one DEO and one AEO. Simple random sampling was used to select the teachers, students and the AEO. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the DEO. Data collection tools used were structured and unstructured questionnaires, interview schedules and document analysis. Content validity and test re-test techniques were used to validate and test instrument reliability respectively. A Pearson Correlation coefficient of 0.5 provided the benchmark for instrument reliability. Descriptive statistics was used in data analysis hence Quantitative data was presented using

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frequency counts, means and percentages with the aid of the SPSS Version 16.0. Thematic trends were used to analyze qualitative data hence results of data analysis were presented in form of frequency distribution tables, bar graphs, and pie charts. The study established that: Students in the sub-county had low motivation for academic achievement in both attending school and learning through lessons. They did not make sufficient academic consultations with their various subject teachers. They had problems with indiscipline cases while in school. Academic achievement of the students in Hamisi sub-county's public secondary schools was seen as below expected standards. Students who had scored highly in primary school's KCPE receded academically at the secondary school's final examination (KCSE). Low academic achievement in Hamisi sub-county was a resultant effect of student low motivation for academic achievement and poor discipline. It was recommended that: Secondary schools should be encouraged to seek ways of motivating students and sustaining that motivational level. The schools should also embrace the right disciplinary procedure to address issues of indiscipline in schools. This researcher hoped that this research's findings would be vital for Hamisi sub-county public secondary schools, the Education Office and the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology in general for they will derive insight from it to help solve the issues so highlighted. Future researchers may also derive valuable insight from the findings for purposes of making better their own research works.

Keywords: academic, motivation, discipline, achievement, factors, impact, effect, student

1. Background of the Study

Students are the central point of attention and concern in any school setting. All energies and resources are pulled together and augmented to fulfill their needs and purposes for which they attend school. To achieve intended goals of high academic grades, these researchers were of the view that student motivation should remain high at all times.

Academic achievement of students in public secondary schools in Hamisi sub-county for the period 2011 – 2014 has depicted a gloomy picture of underachievement. High performing primary school students recede academically when results in national primary school examination (KCPE) are compared to the respective performance at the secondary school (KCSE). The begging question pends as to what may be the cause to this phenomenon. Table 1 below shows survey results carried out on 4265 form four

candidates for the years 2011 – 2014. Each student's KCSE score was analyzed vis-à-vis the KCPE score. The worrying trend of academic underachievement was conspicuous. See the figures 1 and 2 below:

Figure 1: KCPE Academic Achievement (2011 – 2014)

Source: Fieldwork (2015)

n = 4,265

Figure 2: KCSE Academic Achievements (2011 – 2014)

Source: Fieldwork (2015)

n = 4,265

From the two figures above, it should be noted that many students (71.4%) who had scored a C+ or above had performed dismally (33.8%) at secondary school's KCSE examination four years later. These researchers were triggered to determine the role of student academic motivation and academic discipline in their academic achievement.

Motivation has been defined as a process that starts with physiological and psychological deficiency (need) that activates behaviour or drive that is aimed at a goal or incentive (Okumbe, 1998). The motivation process thus comprises of needs or deficiencies which set up drives or motives. They are these drives that push one in attempting to acquire incentives or goals (ibid). Okumbe (1998) cites McClelland's theory which relates an education system in reference to student motivation to perform highly apart from the desire to stay in school. The Achievement Motivation shows that a person's motivation patterns are a reflection of his/her environment including family, school, workplace or church (McClelland, 1961).

Student motivation to learn and achieve academically should be cultivated and sustained. This will in the end yield high academic grades and may lead to a culture in a school in which students become self-starters thus self-directing themselves towards achieving high test scores. Asikhia and Michael (2010) asserted that poor student motivational orientation is a major factor leading to lack of interest by student in school programmes. They add that bad peer groups affect motivation of students negatively on top of cracking their pattern of behaviour with especial touch on their attitude, interest and value systems.

David (2007) defined discipline as a concept used to mean the moral capacity or disposition which when engrained in the human personality becomes a powerful habit for self-control. Eson (1965) sums it up by saying that the kind of authority that prevails generally in the class is both a reflection of the social philosophy of that society and a source of that philosophy. A society with strong authoritarian overtones in its political life, for example, will tend to encourage coercion and punitive methods of classroom control, (Eson, 1965)

This researcher opined that poor student discipline has a definite negative impact on their academic achievement. Those well-behaved students are likely to perform better than the undisciplined ones. Quality relationship between student and teachers, as per Marzano and Marzano (2003), yields good discipline among students and that this leads to positivity towards learning by students. Such students are not likely to recede in their academic achievement.

Ombira and Aluko (2011-2012), found out in their study that the trickle-down effect of student indiscipline negatively impacts on the quality of education thus contributing to academic underachievement among secondary school students. On the same note, Njambi and Ogola (2011-2012) noted that student discipline is a pre-requisite to almost everything that a school has to offer. For the goals of a school such as good academic achievement to be realized, they added, a certain level of discipline must exist.

Aremu (2000) depicts that many research works have shown that nature of parental discipline affects academic output of the children. He points out that students from democratic type of parenting perform better than the autocratic ones. The former students are usually strong-willed and read for success in their academics. On the flip side, the latter, whose parents are authoritative, have low self-worth, insecurity and have difficulty in consulting teachers. They also tend to be rebellious thus suffer from academic underachievement in the end. The late 1980s and in '90s saw a high degree of indiscipline cases in several secondary schools in Kenya as documented by David (2007). Three resultant effects of these cases of student unrest were: loss of human life,

property and precious time for learning. A presidential committee on student unrest and indiscipline was consequently formed in 1991 (Sagini, 1991). The committee was to investigate major causes of the problem and suggest possible solutions. If not prevented, it was believed, student indiscipline could still lead to the aforementioned thus worsen the problem of academic underachievement among the secondary school students.

Frankena and Myles (1970) noted that the role of discipline is merely to correct fault, to prevent bad habits, to restrain unruliness, to free the will from the despotism of desires, to keep man's animalism from interfering with his humanity. To a student, indiscipline behaviour is bound to interfere with his/her academics negatively. Disciplinary cases may lead to physical or corporal punishments so that offenders are 'corrected'. Many teachers in sub-Sahara Africa still use this scheme of discipline despite the professional training they undergo (David, 2007).

In Kenya, corporal punishment was outlawed via Legal Notice no. 56/2001 by the Education Ministry but still, over 15 years later, the vice is still on. In spite of this, however, the raging debate still begs '*is the removal of corporal punishment yielding the best outcomes in matters discipline and hence academic achievement?*' If yes, then, '*why should students continue to underachieve academically?*' Sagini (1991) puts it that the importance of student discipline to learning cannot be gainsaid. As cited by David (2007), Sagini (1991) lamented that some disciplinary cases in schools transcended from the administration's and teachers' undoing but the blame and wrath falls back to the students in terms of academic underachievement.

2. Statement of the Problem

Both student academic motivation and discipline have been scored as essential and especial prerequisites to high academic achievement by students with a disregard to the level of education (background of this study). Low academic achievement could be a direct manifestation of nonexistence of the two aspects.

The dismal performance of students in Hamisi sub-county's public secondary schools has always left a bitter pill for students, parents and other stakeholders to swallow. The anticipation of both students and their parents has been sky high the moment good to excellent primary school's KCPE results are released. This anticipation never comes to pass since most of these students tend to return lower grades at KCSE four years later. This, consequently, indicates that there exist factors leading to this dismal achievement. Among these factors, as per these researchers, could be student motivation and discipline hence this study.

3. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect of student academic motivation and discipline as student-related factors contributing to students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county, Vihiga County - Kenya with specific attention on high performing students in primary school who could not return a higher grade in secondary school which truly is against expectation.

4. Research Objectives

This study was guided by the following objectives:

1. To determine the effect of students' motivation to students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county.
2. To ascertain student discipline levels and its effect to student' academic achievement in secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county.

5. Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of students' motivation and its effect to students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county?
2. What is the extent of student discipline and its effect to students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county?

6. Conceptual Framework

The framework below (Figure 3) shows the relationship established between the dependent and the independent variables in this research work. Motivation for academic achievement and student academic discipline formed the independent variables while the students' academic achievement in secondary school's KCSE examination was the dependent variable.

Figure 3: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher, 2016

7. Research Design

This researcher adopted a descriptive survey research design for this study. Kombo and Tromp (2000) and Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) all provide merits of descriptive studies such as: ability to restrict themselves to fact finding, aid in generation of knowledge and solutions to pertinent problems and allowing researchers to collect information by interviewing or issuing questionnaires to sampled individuals. Data collected can also easily be classified, analyzed, compared and interpreted.

7.1 Target Population

A total of 3,826 students, 41 Principals and 428 teachers drawn from all the 41 public secondary schools in Hamisi sub-county were targeted. The education office involving the 2 AEOs and the DEO also formed the target group. Only the students who had written their final secondary school examination (KCSE) were involved. The summary is as in table 1 below. In total, the research targeted 4,298 persons.

Table 1: Target Population (N = 4,298)

Divisions	Schools	Principals	Teachers	Students	AEO	DEO
Tiriki West	24	24	251	2581	1	1
Tiriki East	17	17	177	1245	1	
Total	41	41	428	3826	2	1

Source: DEO's Office, 2015

7.2 Sample Size and Sampling Procedures

A sample of 12 public secondary schools, 12 Principals, 128 teachers and 383 secondary school graduates (years 2011-2014) were selected using simple random sampling technique. This technique allows each member of a population an equal chance of being selected besides allowing room for the generalization of the yielded data and subsequent findings to the entire population (ibid). The study area was split into two strata i.e. Tiriki West and Tiriki East. Stratified random sampling was used to classify public secondary schools in the two strata. With this, proportional representation of the population from the sub-county was achieved (Kombo and Tromp, 2000). Purposive sampling procedure was used to select one District Education Officer (DEO). One Area Education Officer (AEO) was selected using simple random sampling.

Naisuma's (2000) Coefficient of variation was used to select sample size of public secondary schools, teachers and students. The sample size of between 20%-30% is same as that proposed by Best and Khan (2003). Such sample size is ideal in providence of reliable data when selected randomly. Therefore, in this study, the schools, Principals and teachers was selected using the figure recommended above. For the students, Kombo and Tromp (2000) recommendation of a 10% - 30% sample size was used. See table 2 below for the summarized figures.

Table 2: Sample size (n = 525)

Divisions	Schools	Principals	Teachers	Students	AEO	DEO
Tiriki West	7	7	75	258	1	1
Tiriki East	5	5	53	125	1	
Total	12	12	128	383	1	1

Source: Hamisi Sub-county DEO's Office, 2015

7.3 Data Collection Tools

The researchers used questionnaires, interviews and document analysis to collect data.

7.4 Validity and Reliability

7.4.1 Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

Kombo and Tromp (2000) define validity of a test as a measure of how well a test measures what it is supposed to measure. Mugenda and Mugenda (1999) expounds by saying validity is the degree to which results are obtained from the analysis of the data actually represents the phenomena under study. To improve on validity of data collection instruments, the researcher sought the assistance of supervisors who, being experts in research, helped to make the instruments better especially on content

validity. As Wiersma (1995) puts it, content validity is used to establish representation of the items with respect to the objective of the study.

7.4.2 Data Collection and Analysis

This researcher obtained all the necessary authority documentations from relevant bodies which included: Mount Kenya University, Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, the National Council for Science Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI), County and sub-county authorities for purposes of identification and authority for data collection. Imminent respondents were then duly informed of the study through writing with questionnaires being delivered to them later. Interviews were also carried out with the Principals and the education officers. All respondents were assured of the highest degree of confidentiality with which data provided by them was to be treated.

The quantitative data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and results presented using frequency counts, means and percentages with the aid of the SPSS Version 16.0. Qualitative data was analyzed thematically hence results of data analysis were presented in form of frequency distribution tables, bar graphs, and pie charts.

8. Findings and Discussions

8.1 Demographic Data

A. Gender of Respondents

There were more male than females teachers as depicted by a higher number, 67(55.4%), representing the males while 54(44.6%) being females. The same was true with principals since 3 (25.0%) were females while 9 (75.0%) were males. Male students' number was also higher at 182(58.4%) while the female student number was 129(41.6%). Both the DEO and the AEO were male.

Table 3 shows the gender distribution of the respondents who took part in the study.

Table 3: Gender of respondents

Category of respondents	Total number	Male	Female
Principals	12	9 (75.0%)	3 (25.0%)
Teachers	121	67 (54.5%)	54 (44.6%)
Students	311	182 (58.4%)	129 (41.6%)
DEO	1	1 (100%)	0 (0.0%)
AEO	1 (100%)	1 (100%)	0 (0.0%)

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

The higher number of males as shown in the table and figures above could suggest that there were more males among the target population than females. The finding is true to what World Bank (1998) report on overall status of women in Africa. Women's participation in national educational systems is biased due to the socio-cultural and economic environments. Women are seen to be inferior and even the political environment does not favour them. They lag behind almost in all aspects, education notwithstanding. It is largely assumed that educating women would make them too independent thus make them deviate from their roles such as looking after the children, their husbands and the homestead (World Bank, 1998).

B. Age of Respondents

The ages of principals, teachers, the DEO and the AEO were as depicted in table 4 below. For the students, whose number formed the bulk of the whole respondents, their ages were as shown in table 5. See both tables 4 and 5 below.

Table 4: Age of Respondents – Principals, Teachers, DEO and AEO.

Category of Respondents	Age brackets				Total
	30 or below	30 - 39	40 - 49	50 or above	
Principals	0 (0.0%)	3 (25%)	5 (41.7%)	4 (33.3%)	12 (100%)
Teachers	38 (31.4%)	47 (38.9%)	31(25.6%)	5(4.1%)	121 (100%)
DEO	-	-	1 (100%)	-	-
AEO	-	-	1 (100%)	-	-

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

Table 5: Age of Respondents – Students

Age Bracket	15 – 17	18 – 19	20 – 21	Above 21	Total
No. of students	24 (7.7%)	190 (61.1%)	61 (19.6%)	36 (11.6%)	311 (100%)

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

As indicated in the tables above, it was established that none of the principals was aged below 30 years. Most principals, 5(41.7%), were aged 40 – 49 years while 3(25%) principals had their age lying within bracket 30 – 39 years. The largest number was 5 (41.7%) whose age fell between 40 – 49 years while 4(33.3%) principals had their ages at 50 or above. Considering this age brackets, it was worthwhile noting that all the principals were mature individuals whose median age revolved around 40 - 49 years.

Studies carried out on age and decision-making suggest that adults (persons above 26 years) have developed varied and sophisticated ways to contrast the elements that affect a decision (Maria et al., 2007). This could be the result of past exposure and experiences. Having the highest number (41.7%) of principals within the age bracket of

40 – 49, the researcher opined that these principals were better placed to lead the schools in Hamisi sub-county well. On the side of teachers, 38 (31.4%) were aged 30 years and below. A total of 47(38.9%) had ages between 30 – 40 years, 31 (25.6%) had ages between 40 – 49 years. 5(4.1%) teachers were aged above 50 years. For students, 24(7.7%) were aged between 15 – 17 years. A total of 190 (61.1%) were between 18 – 19 years of age with a total of 61 or (19.6%) falling in the 20 – 21 age bracket. Finally, 36 students, 11.6%, were above 21 years of age at the time they did their KCSE. Both the DEO and the AEO had their ages between 40 – 49 years.

C. Student Motivation for Academic Achievement

This researcher aimed at collecting data to ascertain the level of student motivation towards schooling and academics. This aspect was conceptualized by the first three items of questionnaires for principals/teachers and students. The aspects considered were: students' liking towards attending school every day, the extent to which learners exhibited interest in learning through lessons and voluntary subject consultations with teachers. See the tables below (Tables 6 and 7) showing results from the student and teacher respondents.

Table 6: Students' Responses on Motivation for Academic Achievement

Issue	SA (5)	A (4)	UD (3)	DA (2)	SD (1)
I liked attending school every day because I knew I could thus improve my scores.	33 [10.6%]	47 [15.1%]	57 [18.3%]	101 [32.5%]	73 [23.5%]
Most lessons were interesting because I learned new things.	25 [8.0%]	40 [12.9%]	41 [13.2%]	138 [44.4%]	67 [21.5%]
I always voluntarily made subject consultations with my teachers.	23 [7.4%]	48 [15.4%]	35 [11.3%]	124 [39.9%]	81 [26.0%]

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

KEY: SA – Strongly Agree A – Agree UD – Undecided DA – Disagree SD – Strongly Disagree

Data on the aspects above regarding student motivation for academic achievement were also sought from the teachers. See the results of their responses in table7 below.

Table 7: Teachers' Responses on Motivation for Academic Achievement

Issue	SA (5)	A (4)	UD (3)	DA (2)	SD (1)
Students liked attending school every day.	11.6%	16.5%	17.4%	29.7%	25.0%
	[14]	[20]	[21]	[36]	[30]
Most learners exhibited great interest in learning through lessons.	9.9%	14.0%	11.6%	37.2%	27.3%
	[12]	[17]	[14]	[45]	[33]
Students made frequent voluntary subject consultations with teachers.	8.3%	15.7%	9.9%	33.9%	32.2%
	[10]	[19]	[12]	[41]	[39]

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

The data showed that 33(10.6%) of the student respondents strongly agreeing to the statement that students liked attending school every day. A further 47(15.1%) agreed slightly to the same statement (see Table 6). These figures were equally low when compared to findings from teacher respondents in that only 14(11.8%) and 20(16.5%) of the teachers strongly agreed and agreed slightly that students liked attending school (see Table 7). A further 57(18.3%) and 101(32.5%) of the students were undecided and disagreed with the statement respectively. A total of 73(23.5%) students strongly disagreed that they liked attending school every day while 36 [29.7%] and 30[25.0%] of the teachers disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that students did like attending school.

Not many of the parents seemed to understand the importance of regular school attendance for their children. Consequently, they found no motivation to encourage the children to go to school. By failing to register unquestionable level of love towards going to school every day, it was observed that most of these students lack motivation for schooling.

Since interest builds motivation towards something, these researchers also sought to find the interest of students towards learning through lessons to establish the students' levels on the same aspect. The figures showed that 138(44.4%) and 67(21.5%) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively implying that most of them did not exhibit interest in learning (Table 6). A total of 25(8.0%) and 40(12.9%) of the student respondents strongly agreed and agreed slightly to the aspect of: '*students' interest in learning through lessons*'. A further 41(13.2%) were undecided. Regarding teachers, the highest percentage, 37.2% (45) disagreed that most learners exhibited great interest in learning through lesson. A further 27.3% (33) strongly disagreed with the statement. Only 12(9.9%) and 17(14.0%) of the teachers observed that students had great interest in learning by strongly agreeing and agreeing slightly with the statement.

Student academic consultation sought by students from their teachers was considered an indication of high level of motivation in the students. Such students, as

per the researchers, had a high level intrinsic motivation to understand theories and principals with the knowledge that this would make them excel academically. On this aspect of academic consultation, this researcher found out that 124(39.9%) and 81(26.0%) of the students disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that they made subject consultation with their teachers. Since the summation of the two exceeds 65%, it stood out evidently that subject consultation was not done by most students in Hamisi sub-county secondary schools. Only small numbers of 23(7.4%) and 48(15.4%) of the students strongly agreed and agreed slightly to having made voluntary subject consultations.

The remaining 35(11.3%) of the student respondents were undecided on the issue. The teachers from whom the subject consultation was to be sought disagreed and strongly disagreed by 33.9% (41) and 32.3% (39) respectively that students went to them seeking subject consultation. A few teachers, precisely 10(8.3%) and 19(15.7%) respectively, however, strongly agreed and agreed slightly that students voluntarily sought these services.

D. Student Academic Discipline

This researcher also sought to find out and analyze data on students' level of academic discipline in respect to their academic achievement. To achieve this, three aspects were sought from the respondents. These were: subject consultations done by students with teachers, students getting deterred from lessons due to indiscipline cases, finishing given assignments on time and score correctly by students. Data yielded from respondents was as shown in the tables below.

Figure 4 shows the student responses on the three aspect used by these researchers to find out the level of student academic discipline towards academic achievement. See the results below.

Figure 4: Students' responses on Student Discipline

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

n = 311

Data from teachers' responses on Student Discipline was as shown in the next figure below. See Figure 5 to peruse the data findings.

Figure 5: Teachers' responses on Student Discipline

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

n = 121

This researcher also sought to collect data from the principals on how they viewed the students in terms of their academic discipline towards academic achievement. See Figure 6 to peruse the data findings.

Table 6: Principals' Responses on Student Academic Discipline

Source: Fieldwork (2016)

n = 12

As indicated in the preceding section, subject consultation by students skewed towards the strongly disagree side. This can be seen from Figure 4 above. The data from students showed that 124(39.9%) of the student respondents disagreeing that they sought subject consultation from their teachers. Data from the teachers also informed that 40(33.1%) of them disagreed slightly while 39[32.2%] strongly disagreeing (see Figure 5). The principals, however, indicated that voluntary subject consultation by students was above average in that 5(41.7%) and 2(16.7%) agreed slightly and agreed strongly respectively to the statement: *Students made frequent subject consultations with teachers* (see Figure 6). A further 4(33.3%) and 1(8.3%) of the principals disagreed and strongly disagreed that students consulted their teachers on academics. These findings contrasted with that from students and teachers. The researcher opined that the principals ensured that students consulted teachers on areas of weaknesses in various subjects. These consultations were most likely a forced practice as seen by many of the student respondents disagreeing to making voluntary consultations.

Student academic discipline was tested through finding the frequency with which the students got deterred from lessons due to indiscipline cases. Findings from students showed that 116(37.3%) agreed slightly to the statement that they got deterred from lessons due to indiscipline reasons (see table 4). Another 47(15.1%) and 29(9.3%) of

the students disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that they got deterred from attending lessons due to cases of indiscipline. The remaining 35(11.3%), however, were undecided on this issue. Regarding teachers, a higher percentage seemed to agree that students in their schools missed lessons due to indiscipline cases probably occasioned by, among other reasons, suspensions. This was seen by 49(40.5%) and 35(28.9%) of them agreeing and strongly agreeing to the statement. Only 11(9.1%) and 14(11.6%) of the teachers disagreed and strongly disagreed that students got deterred from lessons due to indiscipline cases (See Figure 5). A combined 9(75.0%) of the principals also indicated that students poor disciplined made them miss classes with 1(8.3%) and 2(16.7%) disagreeing strongly and disagreeing slightly that students had issues with discipline and hence missed classes (Figure 6).

Student academic discipline also involves doing classwork and assignments correctly and on time, this researcher found out that 109(35.0%) and 78(25.1%) of the students disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively to the issue of finishing academic assignments on time and scoring correctly (Figure 4). The teacher respondents also provided data akin to this in that 45(37.2%) and 18(14.9%) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively to this very statement (Figure 5). A further 66(21.2%) and 27(8.7%) of the students agreed and strongly agreed respectively implying that they did and got classwork and assignments right within time given. The remaining 31(10.0%) were undecided. Only 11(9.1%) and 30(24.8%) of the teachers opined that students did and finished assignments correctly and on time by strongly agreeing and agreeing slightly respectively.

It can be pointed out from the data above that the state of student academic discipline in secondary schools in Hamisi Sub County was wanting for the period 2011 – 2014. From this data, it is evident that most students got deterred from lessons due to indiscipline cases, did not finish given assignments on time and score correctly and only few made subject consultations with their teachers.

From the interview schedule, the respondents (principals) were to rate the status of student discipline on three fronts of Good, Average and Bad. A total of 4(33.3%) principals said that the discipline of students in their schools for the period 2011 - 2014 was good with 3(25%) vehemently saying that discipline was bad. 5(41.7%) said that there was an average standard of discipline in their schools. The principals highlighted problems related to discipline such as: pregnancy, drug abuse and truancy. A few 4(33.3%) asserted that the task of instilling discipline in students had been left to the teaching staff and the administration. One principal was quoted saying:

“Some parents had the audacity to bring even domestic indiscipline cases of their children to school for onward punishment because ‘these children have overpowered us’. Four students in this school did their KCSE examination last years (2014) while pregnant.”

9. Summary of the Major Findings

9.1 Motivation for Academic Achievement

It was generally seen that student motivation for academic achievement was not good enough. This was shown by 101[32.5%] and 73[23.5%] of the students disagreeing and strongly disagreeing that students liked attending school. Only 14(11.6%) and 20(16.5%) of the teachers strongly agreed and agreed slightly that students liked attending school. Data on students' interest in learning through lessons showed that 138(44.4%) and 67(21.5%) of the students disagreed slightly and strongly disagreed respectively implying that most of them did not exhibit interest in learning. The highest number of teachers, 45 (37.2%), disagreed that most learners exhibited great interest in learning through lesson. A further 27.3% (33) strongly disagreed with the statement. This indicated that students lacked motivation towards their academics thus they did not see the need of sitting in class and learning through lessons.

As regards subject consultations done by students from their teachers, these researchers found out that 124(39.9%) and 81(26.0%) of the students disagreed flatly and strongly disagreed respectively that they sought subject consultation from their teachers. The teachers affirmed this by disagreeing slightly and strongly disagreeing by 33.9% (41) and 32.2% (39) respectively that students went to them seeking subject consultation. Low motivation can be an attribute of, according to Gokce (2013), syllabus density, overloading, health problems, traditional teaching methods, boring and colourless lessons, too many similar type exercises and questions and shortage of materials.

9.2 Student Academic Discipline

Data regarding students' academic discipline showed that 124(39.9%) students strongly disagreed that they sought voluntary subject consultation from their teachers (Figure 4). Data from the teachers also informed that 41(33.9%) of them disagreeing slightly while 39[32.2%] strongly disagreeing (see Figure 5). Most principals, however, indicated that voluntary subject consultation by students was appealing in that 5(41.7%) and 2(16.7%) agreed slightly and agreed strongly respectively that students consulted teachers on matters academics.

Findings from students showed that 116(37.3%) agreed slightly to the statement that they got deterred from lessons due to indiscipline reasons while 84[27.0%] agreed strongly. The teachers seemed to indicate that many students stayed away from class due to indiscipline cases by 35(28.9%) and 49(40.5%) of them strongly agreeing and agreeing slightly to this aspect. At 25% (3) and 50.0 % (6) principals strongly agreed and agreed slightly that students got deterred from lesson due to being undisciplined.

Doing classwork and assignments correctly and on time was considered an aspect of academic discipline, these researchers found out that 109(35.0%) and 78(25.1%) of the students disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively to the issue of finishing academic assignments on time and scoring correctly (Figure 4). Only 11(9.1%) and 30(24.8%) (see Figure 5) of the teachers opined that students did and finished assignments correctly and on time by strongly agreeing and agreeing slightly respectively. Through interviews, the principals were to rate the status of student discipline on three fronts of Good, Average and Bad. The principals' responses were that: 4(33.3%) of them said student discipline in their schools were Good, 3(25%) said it was bad while 5(41.7%) indicated that there was an Average level of discipline in their schools for the period 2011 – 2014 (Figure 6). According to the principals, drug abuse, truancy among students, and irresponsible behaviour leading to pregnancies, careless parents were seen as major issues imparting negatively on student discipline.

10. Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study as summarized above, it was concluded that:

1. Students in the sub-county had low motivation for academic achievement in both attending school and learning through lessons. They did not make sufficient academic consultations with their various subject teachers.
2. Students had problems with indiscipline cases while in school. Drug abuse, truancy and irresponsible behaviour leading to pregnancies were pinpointed as issues affecting student discipline.
3. Academic achievement of the students in Hamisi sub-county was seen as below expected standards. Students who had scored highly in primary school's KCPE receded academically at the secondary school's final examination (KCSE).
4. Low academic achievement in Hamisi sub-county was a resultant effect of student low motivation for academic achievement and poor discipline.

11. Recommendations

1. Secondary schools should be encouraged to seek ways of motivating students and sustaining that motivational level. This should be through ensuring students are attended to in class, their issues are addressed amicably on top of inviting mentors and motivational speakers to talk to the students.
2. The schools should embrace the right disciplinary procedures to address issues of indiscipline in schools. Guiding and counseling departments should be put in place and made operational.
3. Schools should help learners set academic achievement targets and guide them in achieving those targets right from Form One of secondary schooling.

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